

Atra-Hasīs

also known as “Epic of Atra-Hasīs”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Babylonian Religions, Text, Excavated text, Ancient Mesopotamian Text, Mesopotamian Religion, Ancient Babylonian Text, Semitic, East Semitic, Language, Afro-Asiatic, Akkadian

The Epic of Atra-Hasīs is an Old Babylonian poem that narrates the story of the man who survived the Flood. The best-preserved edition of the text known by the ancient Mesopotamians as enūma ilū awēlum (“When the Gods Were Man”) is dated to the reign of Ammi-Šaduqa of Babylon (c. 1702-1682 BCE), as evidenced by the colophon, which also preserves the name of the scribe responsible for the edition, Kasaq-Aya (or Nūr-Aya). Divided into three tablets, each with eight columns of about fifty-five lines, the composition recounts two different stories, the first of which refers to the deities and the creation of humanity to free them from the burden of work, the second to the near-destruction of the human race by the Flood. Despite divine’s intentions, the creation of the human being led to its uncontrolled reproduction and the consequent noise that disturbed the celestial sphere. The head of the pantheon, god Enlil, thus decided to convene a “war council” and after sending several afflictions to decrease the number of humans, he finally decided to send the Flood to wipe out humanity. Nevertheless, using his powers, god Enki instructed an “extraordinary wise” man (meaning of the name Atra-Hasīs in Akkadian) to build a vessel and save humankind from destruction. As a consequence of his actions, Atra-Hasīs was granted immortality, and the deities took a series of measures in order to prevent overpopulation. Besides the Old Babylonian tablets from Sippar, other Middle and Late Babylonian fragments of the composition were exhumed at Babylon, Nippur, Ugarit, and Sippar. Plus, a Late Assyrian edition was recovered from Ashurbanipal’s (c. 668-627 BCE) library in Nineveh. Furthermore, although Atra-Hasīs is the best-known poetic text related to the Flood, additional testimonies of the same story have been found in ancient Mesopotamia. In Sumerian written evidence from roughly the same period as the earlier copies of Atra-Hasīs, the Deluge hero bears the name Ziusudra (i.e. the one who lived a “life of long days”). Accordingly, in the Flood story preserved on tablet XI of the Epic of Gilgamesh, the survivor of the Flood is known as Uta-napištim, meaning “the one who found life”.

Date Range: 1700 BCE - 600 BCE

Region: Ancient Mesopotamia

Region tags: Iraq, Syria

A rough map of the ancient Near Eastern region of Mesopotamia.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Wilfred G. Lambert & Alan R. Millard, 1969. *Atra-Hasīs. The Babylonian Story of the Flood*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.

– Source 2: Andrew George & F. N. H. Al-Rawi, 1996. “Tablets from the Sippar Library VI. Atra-ḫasīs”. *Iraq* 58: 147-190.

– Source 3: Ignacio Márquez Rowe, 2016. “Two Middle Babylonian Atra-ḫasīs Tablets from Babylon”. *Aula Orientalis* 34/1: 57-70.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/etcsl.cgi?text=t.1.7.4#>

– Source 1 Description: The Sumerian Flood Story

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Incised or Inscribed

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Method of inscription

– Other [specify]: Stylus

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Clay

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Clay object

– Clay tablet

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Content

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the description of the creation of the human being, the text traces a distinction between the physical body, which would be formed from clay, and the spirit - the *eṭemmu* - which would be created from the blood of a sacrificed deity and corresponded to the part of the human being that survived after death.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: The supreme high god Enlil is responsible for sending a series of catastrophes in order to wipe out humanity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

Notes: Enlil seems unaware of the fact that Atra-Hasis builds a boat and saves himself and his kins from the catastrophe, thus contradicting his plans to decimate humanity. By the end of the epic, Enlil questions how it was possible for a man to survive the Flood.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

Notes: In Atra-Hasis, Enlil's behavior is mainly negative, although in other compositions it can be positive.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– Yes

Notes: Enlil, as the other deities, experiences hunger and weeps when humankind is afflicted by the Flood and the gods cease to be fed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can be tricked?

– Yes

Notes: Enlil is tricked by god Enki who cunningly warns a human being, Atra-Hasis, through a dream, of the imminence of the Flood.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– No

Notes: In the Epic of Atra-Hasis, Enlil communicates mainly with other deities, although in other Mesopotamian compositions he communicates directly with the human being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

Notes: As mentioned, although the gods have the ability to foresee the future, Enlil seems to be unaware of the plan devised by Enki together with Atra-Hasis.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ In trance possession?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: In addition to experiencing the pangs of hunger, supernatural beings feel disillusioned and cry.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: The text mentions various entities that work together with the gods, such as the lahmu-heroes who watched over the sea or the pašittu-demons who were in charge of kidnapping babies in order to prevent overpopulation..

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Libations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Food?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Daily life objects?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: Enlil is surprised to learn that Enki planned the survival of the human race, going against his will.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: In the epic, the creation of humanity intends to solve a problem that has to do precisely with the rivalry between the Anunnaki, the group of deities that depended on the work carried out by the Igigi, their counterpart. It is from the revolt and "strike" of the latter that the need to create a solution arises.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done only by high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

Notes: No, although the application of a divine "punishment" serves to control the multiplication of human beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Notes: See above

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done randomly

– No

Notes: See above

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Political failure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

Notes: Before the Flood, the gods send out plagues, diseases, drought and famine.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

Notes: By the end of the epic, the gods decree that among humankind there will be barren women, stillbirths, and those who will be forbidden to give birth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done only by high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

Notes: Yes if one considers that after Atra-Hasis instructs the elders to worship certain gods, the plagues and droughts sent by them end, giving way to good weather.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

Notes: Although it is not explicit in this epic, we know from other stories about the flood that he who survived the catastrophe was granted immortality by the gods.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: Atra-Hasis is a wise man because he "kept his ear opened" to the gods and performed worship and sacrifices.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: The text, although fragmented, seems to make reference to a distinction between pure and impure animals, as we will find later in the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Cooperation

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Drama?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that the text was recited orally.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Comedy?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Tragedy?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Epic entertainment?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are they mandatory?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

Notes: The text clearly states that the gods smell the fragrance of Atra-Hasis' sacrifice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Although the literate community in ancient Mesopotamia was small, the majority would be made up of male individuals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– Yes

Notes: Although the text is quite fragmented in the part that corresponds to the description of the items that Atra-Hasis boarded in his boat, it seems that food and animals were referred to.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions the revolt of the Igigi against the Anunnaki. They go to the house of their chief, Enlil, after burning their work tools and prepare for battle.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Notes: The beginning of the epic mentions the work carried out by the gods, which would certainly result in the production of food. The work involved irrigating the land through its two main rivers, the Tigris and the Euphrates.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Mesopotamia

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